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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE 4K MODEL IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Annotation: *The article highlights the problems and solutions in organizing the independent creative activities of future primary school teachers. It reveals the unique features of completing creative tasks in preparing future teachers and analyzes effective methods to improve students' skills and abilities in creative work. The main component of the teaching process is the lesson. The educational activity of the teacher and the student is primarily focused on the lesson. Therefore, the quality of teaching students a specific academic discipline largely depends on the level of organization of the lesson.*

Key Words: *activity, systematicity, independence, skills, creative work.*

INTRODUCTION

This article aims to study the problems of independent creative activities of future primary school teachers and propose solutions to these problems. Effective methods for enhancing students' skills and abilities in creative work are analyzed. As a component of the teaching process, the activities of the teacher and student are mainly focused on the lesson, and the quality of teaching students a specific academic discipline is determined by the level of organization.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Education with an emphasis on the creativity of primary school students requires addressing the issue of interpreting students as subjects of the educational process. Based on this foundation, it is important to describe the principle of interpreting students' creativity within a "subject-object" system. Personal qualities developed in students during the educational process—such as awareness, independence, and resourcefulness—are not solely the result of the teacher's work but are also largely dependent on the students themselves. Adhering to this principle, educational material is regarded as a subject of activity, and components of creative activity are identified.[1] Today, educational-methodological complexes (EMCs) used in the presentation of new-generation textbooks are introduced. These complexes implement the principles of Critical Thinking, Collaboration, Creativity, and Communication (4C). These technologies play a crucial role in enhancing the learning process and developing textbooks that are engaging and effective for students. Educational-methodological complexes are developed based on global programs (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, EGMA, EGRA) and are used in the study of exemplary tasks employed in assessing students' achievements. They include textbooks, exercise books, and methodological guides for teachers.[2] The Estudy electronic education platform is also developed in accordance with these complexes. The platform includes educational courses in subjects such as mathematics, natural sciences, and computer science, and integrates game-based tasks for students. It is hosted on the TAS-IX network and is available free of charge.

The complexes are compatible with Android and iOS platforms and include interactive games in Uzbek and Russian for mobile applications such as "Mathematics" and "Alphabet." This interactive educational program aims to develop students' essential life skills and foster interest in science in the 21st century. Additionally, some parts of the textbooks designed for grades 1–3, specifically for subjects such as visual arts, Uzbek language, and music literacy, are developed using augmented reality technology. These are created to stimulate students' interest in subjects and teach them important skills.[3] The article emphasizes that these tools are not limited to mathematics, computer science, and natural sciences but also play an important role in equipping students with 21st-century skills and providing interactive teaching methods. In primary education, the 4C principles—Critical Thinking, Collaboration, Creativity, and Communication—represent an educational outcome aimed at effective, modern, and personal development. These principles are vital in creating a successful teaching and learning process for students.

Critical Thinking: Developing students' ability to understand and analyze. This includes analyzing issues, expressing ideas, asking theoretical and practical questions, and logically comprehending educational material.

Collaboration: Promoting group work and enhancing cooperation among students. This involves valuing the opinions of every group member, providing feedback to each other, and solving tasks collectively.

Creativity: Encouraging students to innovate and apply creative approaches. This fosters their ability to express thoughts, solve problems using their ideas, and engage in creative endeavors.

Communication: Enhancing students' communication skills. This involves effectively expressing ideas, information, and concepts to others in a clear and consistent manner.[4]

In primary education, the 4C principles enable students to consistently express their opinions, answer questions, work in groups, seek innovative approaches, and apply them creatively. This principle helps students adapt to the modern world, learn new concepts, and develop independent thinking. The rapid development of technology, globalization, and demographic challenges are actively changing society. In today's globalized era, the knowledge and skills formed in past education systems are insufficient for success in our time. The education system is also revising its objectives and increasingly incorporating broader skills into curricula. The most important skills include social skills, critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving abilities. UNESCO's fundamental international document on education describes "sustainable development goals" and identifies outcomes in cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral learning.[5] Competency (derived from the Latin word meaning "to achieve" or "to fit") refers to the readiness of an individual to organize external and internal resources effectively to achieve a goal. In other words, it is a personal ability to solve specific professional problems. Critical Thinking: This methodology includes developing students' skills in critically evaluating information and forming their own opinions and judgments. It teaches them to approach problems analytically and form perspectives based on logical reasoning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if we aim to help students develop these critical competencies, we need to organize the learning process in a way that enables them to engage in such activities consistently. In primary education, students should not only master the content of subjects through school lessons but also

develop the ability to independently acquire and create knowledge. Most importantly, they should learn self-management and teamwork skills.

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